

Identifying and Displaying EdTech Implementation Context Profiles

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Abstract—Education technology (edtech) is increasingly prevalent in classrooms, yet 85% of the technologies currently implemented are a bad fit for the school, or are poorly implemented. To address this limitation, the EdTech Evidence Exchange has collected survey responses to characterize the contexts in which technologies are being implemented. Their platform is working to leverage educator knowledge and experiences with edtech and connect similar schools. Variable selection via penalized regression and unsupervised methods extracts a subset of the factors that are the most informative in characterizing schools' contexts. This subset is then used to fit a Gaussian Mixture Model to create soft clusters of schools with similar contexts. A new feature, "Schools Like Mine," combines soft classification and Euclidean distance to identify and rank schools by similarity.

Index Terms—education technology, survey responses, variable selection, Gaussian Mixture Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Variable selection is an important method for extracting interpretable knowledge from high-dimensional data. Using a combination of supervised and unsupervised methods is particularly effective at identifying informative variable subsets that may be used in downstream analyses. This method combines results from ridge regression and sparse principal component analysis (PCA) to balance the identification of variables that are related to a response variable with the identification of those that best explain the inherent variance in the data set. The variables identified by this method are then used in cluster analysis.

Identifying a subset of variables that captures important sources of variation in a data set enhances the interpretability of subsequent analyses. The results of cluster analyses informed by a variable subset are easier to understand and communicate, for example, and allow the knowledge gained to yield a broader impact. The variable subset identified as part of this work is used to fit a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) and underlies a matching algorithm that quantifies the similarity between entities and returns a list of the most similar entities to a point of interest.

II. BACKGROUND

The EdTech Evidence Exchange is a non-profit that leverages peer insight to support educators as they make decisions about education technologies (edtech). Started as a for-profit

accelerator for evaluating edtech efficacy, the group shifted their focus to consolidate and share insights from within the education community. The EdTech Evidence Exchange concluded that the context in which a technology is implemented is vitally important in determining the efficacy of its implementation, and that there are currently no efforts to understand these contexts.

A first step in filling this gap was developing the language to describe the context in which these technologies are implemented. The EdTech Genome Project [1] brought together researchers, educators, and industry leaders to develop a common understanding and classification for the educational contexts that matter for edtech. Ultimately, this endeavor defined ten context features, as well as ways to measure them. Each feature was then broken down into a small set of factors via exploratory factor analyses and subsequent confirmatory factor analyses [4]; this process yielded 47 factors total, with three to six factors per context feature.

Since identifying and defining these factors, the Exchange's focus has been on creating a repository to collect and disseminate educator knowledge on EdTech implementation. The EdTech Evidence Exchange Platform collects information through a Context Inventory administered to administrators, principals, and teachers. Currently, the Exchange Platform offers a "Districts Like Mine" feature that uses the inventory data to quantify the degree of similarity between school districts so that educators might use the experiences of educators in similar contexts to inform their decisions surrounding edtech in their district. This algorithm calculates the mean response within a school district for each question in the inventory, and then compares across districts by adding the absolute differences between the focal district's score and the score of all other districts on the Platform for each question. Educators using the Exchange Platform therefore can see how similar another district on the Platform is to their own and integrate that information into their decision-making process.

This method of identifying similar school districts works well enough, but has several limitations. First, while context factors within each of the ten features have been analyzed to prevent redundancy, they have not been examined in aggregate. The Platform also hopes to provide more detailed information to accompany the similarity scores, but this task is too daunting

when all 47 factors are still at play. Finally, there is substantial variation among schools within a single district, so matching at the district level is likely inappropriate. Thus, the goal of this work is to improve the current EdTech Evidence Exchange Platform’s matching algorithm to produce more meaningful and interpretable results. The methods developed below identify the most informative subset of the 47 factors that describe a school’s context and use this knowledge to produce an improved “Schools Like Mine” algorithm that yields school-level matches for Platform users.

III. DATA DESCRIPTION

The data consists of educator responses to the EdTech Context Inventory administered by the Exchange Platform. These survey questions are part of a nested-factors model developed by the EdTech Genome Project (ref). All questions in the inventory map to one of the 47 factors and are on a five-point Likert scale. The data on the Exchange Platform consists of basic identifying information (district ID, school ID, etc.) for each user and their question responses, averaged at the factor level such that values range continuously between one and five.

At the time this research was completed, the data set included responses from 1574 educators (teachers and administrators) from more than ten states around the country. However, 113 responses were removed from the data set on account of a large number (> 10 , or 21.3%) of missing values. The final data set therefore contained factor-level scores from 1461 educators with a limited number of missing values per entry.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methods employed for factor selection and clustering require complete data. Missing values from individuals’ responses are therefore replaced with the average of five iterative imputations (`sklearn, Iterative_Imputer`) [5]; the use of replicas aids with stability among the imputed values. The complete responses are then aggregated at the school level using the mean of each factor. All subsequent methods use this data set.

A. Subset Selection

Working at the school level requires individual responses to be aggregated into a school-level response. In order to ensure equal strength amongst these aggregations, missing values were imputed using (`sklearn, Iterative_Imputer`) [5], and averaged over five imputations to increase the stability of these imputations. Then, these complete responses were collapsed to the school level and aggregated by mean for each factor. The individual-level imputed data is saved nightly, allowing the model bootstrapping methods and “Schools Like Mine” to quickly pull the most up-to-date, complete data on-demand with minimal computation costs.

1) *Ridge Regression*: Although there is no true response variable in the Context Inventory, the Exchange Platform contains other data that measures the experience of edtech implementation in schools. Specifically, the Implementation Survey includes two variables that measure the perceived overall success of edtech implementation as it relates to instruction and student outcomes, respectively. These two variables provide pseudo-response variables that allow ridge regression to be used for variable selection. Ultimately, the goal of the Exchange Platform is for educators to learn from the implementation experiences of others in similar contexts, and so the use of these pseudo-response variables is appropriate in identifying the most important factors defining a school’s context.

Ridge regression is a supervised learning method that applies an L2 norm penalty to shrink linear regression coefficients towards zero with to minimize the residual sum of squares such that

$$\min_w \|Xw - y\|_2^2 + \lambda \|w\|_2^2$$

The L2 norm penalizes the sum of squares of the coefficients, rather than the absolute sum of the weights, and tends to better maintain features in high dimensional space. This penalty shrinks coefficients asymptotically towards zero, but not to zero, so a threshold of 0.05 is used as a cut-off to remove coefficients with little contribution. Ridge regression is done using (`sklearn, Ridge_CV`) [5], which implements cross validation to choose the optimal λ value.

Regressing the data on implementation success raises the concern of biasing factor selection towards those schools that have had successful EdTech implementation in the past. While these factors selected from ridge regression are certainly important, our goal is to find the factors that best differentiate school contexts, not the factors that best predict current implementation success. For this reason, we supplement this method with an unsupervised approach to identify an additional subset of factors.

2) *Sparse PCA*: Sparse PCA is an alteration of Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a common dimension-reduction method. PCA finds linear combinations of the provided variables that explain the most variance in the data, called principal components. It does so by finding the singular value decomposition, \mathbf{X} , such that

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}^T,$$

with $\mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}$ representing the principal components and \mathbf{V} representing the coefficients for the linear combinations of the variables, also called the principal component loadings [6]. Principal components are generated sequentially and capture the maximum variance unexplained by prior components. While PCA effectively maps large amounts of variables into a reduced number of dimensions, the results are often uninterpretable, as all coefficients must be included in all components.

Sparse PCA formulates PCA as a regression maximization problem, adding an L1 norm penalty to allow for sparse load-

ings and the elimination of some variables from the components. While there are various implementations of sparse PCA, `sklearn`'s, `decomposition.SparsePCA` [5] optimizes

$$(U^*, V^*) = \underset{U, V}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \|X - UV\|^2 + \lambda \|V\|_1$$

subject to $\|U_k\|^2 \leq 1$ for all $0 \leq k \leq n_{components}$. V^* are the sparse loadings, and non-zero values represent the factors selected for each respective principal component. The sparsity can be controlled by λ , with higher values leading to sparser loadings. The goal in this implementation of sparse PCA is to produce a subset of factors that is small enough to be interpretable while still retaining as much of the variance as possible [2]. The total variance explained by the sparse loadings is also dependent on the number of principal components chosen to create, as more components will always explain more variance, given that the latest component maximizes the variance explained remaining [2]. We create ten relatively sparse components, and then use the factors found in the first five components to define the factor subset found by sparse PCA. Principal components in regular PCA are required to be orthogonal, and so each component represents a different axis in the variation in the data. While sparse principal components are not orthogonal, they are nearly orthogonal, and so the first 5 components are used to identify factors that represent different axes of the variance. Four λ values (6.5, 7.7, 5.8) were used in this implementation, as they produce sparse enough models from the first five components and still account for roughly half of the total variance.

3) *Combining Factor Subsets*: The prior two approaches yield six factor subsets: two from ridge regression and four from sparse PCA. Factors that appear in at least five of the six subsets are included in the final factor subset. This selection method creates a more robust subset of factors to describe schools' contexts without being overly stringent.

B. Clustering

Following subset selection, the identified factors are used to fit a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to help classify and describe the schools on the Exchange Platform. The optimal number of clusters and covariance type is identified using BIC. Specifically, 20 GMMs are fit for every pairwise combination of the number of clusters (5-20 clusters, though the range may be specified) and covariance type ('full,' 'tied,' 'diag,' and 'spherical') and the combination with the lowest average BIC across replicates was selected. A final GMM is fit using the number of clusters and the covariance type identified through this process, with K-means used to initialize other model parameters (`sklearn.mixture.GaussianMixture`) [5].

1) *Evaluation of Model Stability*: Cluster stability of the GMM is evaluated via bootstrap resampling and calculation of the Jaccard coefficient [3]; this is an important step as GMMs are non-deterministic. The cluster stability algorithm first takes hard cluster classifications from the original dataset and model. Then, for each bootstrapped sample, the data is sampled with replacement and used fit a new, bootstrapped GMM, using

the same parameters as the original. Hard cluster classifications are then calculated from the bootstrapped sample and model. Classifications from the original GMM model are then compared with classifications from the bootstrapped model by using the Jaccard coefficient. The Jaccard coefficient measures the similarity between two sample sets (A, B) as

$$\frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|},$$

or the size of the intersection divided by the size of the union. However, because GMM models are non-deterministic, it is not certain that the first cluster in the bootstrapped model will map onto the first cluster from the original model. For this reason, we binarize all cluster classifications, and compute the Jaccard coefficients for all combinations of original and bootstrapped clusters for each bootstrap. The bootstrapped cluster with the highest Jaccard coefficient for each original cluster is then considered to be the bootstrapped equivalent cluster, and its Jaccard coefficient is stored. Coefficients are averaged across multiple bootstraps. Average Jaccard coefficients greater than 0.5 are considered to be defining the same cluster, and scores ranging 0.6-0.7 are considered "good". This evaluation of cluster stability will be used periodically to ensure model quality.

C. Matching Algorithm

The Exchange Platform currently offers a "Districts Like Mine" service for its clients. This work improves upon this service by producing a "Schools Like Mine" feature from which a Platform user receives a ranked list of up to 20 schools most similar to their institution. A combination of soft clustering from the GMM fit in the previous step and the calculation of the Euclidean distances between schools on the Exchange Platform is used to generate this ranked list. Once integrated into the Exchange Platform, this function will use the most current version of the data, which is imputed nightly, as described at the beginning of the section.

Euclidean distances between all schools on the Exchange platform are calculated using `sklearn.metrics.pairwise_distances` method [5]. Soft clustering from the GMM is then used to narrow down the schools considered for the ranked list. Clusters of interest include those to which the probability of membership to that cluster is at least 5% for the caller's school. Similarly, other schools on the Platform are considered for the ranked list if they belong, with a probability of at least 5%, to one of these identified clusters of interest. Rankings are determined by the Euclidean distance to the caller's school (D), with a shorter distance conferring a higher rank. Finally, the Euclidean distances are converted to a score that is scaled to the maximum distance from the user's school in the Exchange Platform data set (D_{max}). Scores are calculated using the following equation

$$\text{Score} = 1 - \frac{D}{D_{max}}$$

Fig. 1. Subset selection identified 22 factors spanning the ten context features.

such that the most distant school returns a score of zero and a school with factor values identical to the user’s returns a score of one.

This method returns a ranked list of up to 20 schools with the highest similarity scores (the shortest distance) that are identified by their district ID number and school ID number. In the event that fewer than 20 schools are in the clusters of interest, all schools within those clusters are returned.

V. CASE STUDY

The following is an example of how these methods will be applied on the EdTech Evidence Exchange Platform.

A. Subset Selection

Subset selection using data from the Exchange Platform identified 22 of the 47 factors, with representation from all ten context features as seen in Figure 1. The combined use of supervised and unsupervised methods creates a robust set of variables to inform the subsequent analyses: ridge regression gives preference to factors that are influential in predicting implementation success, while sparse PCA considers the broader variance of the data.

As the Exchange Platform grows and incorporates new data, the factor subset is expected to change. Administrators will be able to re-run this method, incorporating the additional information into the Platform’s features.

B. Clustering

After the subset selection process identified 22 factors of importance, that factor subset was used to fit the GMM for clustering at the school level. BIC indicated that the optimal number of groups was 20, and selected a spherical covariance type; the final model was fit using these specifications. Although GMMs provide soft classification, the majority of

schools in the data set at the time of these analyses were classified to a single cluster with a probability $\geq 95\%$. Nonetheless, these methods use soft classification to accommodate changes at the Exchange Platform incorporates additional data.

When integrated into the Exchange Platform, the GMM will be re-fit each time the Subset Selection method is run.

C. Matching Algorithm

On the Exchange Platform, the matching algorithm may be called by (1) a user whose school is already on the Exchange Platform or (2) a user whose school is not yet in the Platform. Both scenarios are described below.

1) *Existing Schools*: To simulate current users, two schools were randomly sampled from the data set and posed at the callers of the “Schools Like Mine” function. The first school received a list of 15 schools from nine districts with scores ranging from 0.8238 to 0.6411. Combined, these 16 schools most likely belongs to a small, distinct cluster. The second school received a list of 20 schools from 12 districts (including its own) with scores ranging from 0.8883 to 0.8167. Based on the list characteristics, this school may belong predominantly to a single large cluster, or display moderate belonging to multiple clusters. The general lack of soft clustering observed (see previous section) indicates that the former is more likely.

2) *A “New” School*: The “Schools Like Mine” feature is available to all Exchange Platform users, regardless of whether their school was on the platform when the GMM was last trained. Thus, random values were generated to simulate a function call from a new school. As these values were entirely random and do not have the relationships that are characteristic of true values, there was no expectation that the algorithm would be able to identify strong matches among the schools on the Exchange Platform; the function will still return a list of the best matches available in the data set. Indeed, this “new” school received a list of 11 schools, each from a unique district, and the scores ranged from 0.5197 to 0.2612.

One important exception to the general availability of the “Schools Like Mine” feature applies to new schools that provide incomplete data. Because the data on the Exchange Platform is imputed nightly, new incomplete responses cannot be immediately integrated into the data set. These users will therefore need to wait until the following day to use this feature.

VI. CONCLUSION

The EdTech Evidence Exchange is a non-profit organization dedicated to the collection and dissemination of knowledge from within the education community to facilitate informed decision-making surrounding education technology. Currently, the Exchange Platform uses its Context Survey to quantify context at the district level, and to identify school districts with similar contexts. The methods described in this paper improve upon this system, leveraging supervised and unsupervised methods to select the factors that most effectively describe a school’s context. This subset is then used in the new “Schools

Like Mine” feature, which identifies similar schools in terms of the most informative context factors.

This approach presents new opportunities to investigate schools’ contexts. The identification of an informative factor subset improves the interpretability of the clusters identified through Gaussian Mixture Modeling; researchers at the Exchange will be able to explore the factors that define each cluster and observe changes as more data is added to the Exchange Platform. The reduction in the number of factors considered may also allow for deeper analysis of the similarities between schools, such as identifying which factors are the most and/or least similar between any two schools. Finally, shifting the level of focus from the district level to the school level exposes contextual variation among schools within a single school district.

Variable selection performed through the combination of supervised and unsupervised methods yields a robust subset of the data that can be used in subsequent analyses. Ridge regression, a supervised method, gives preference to variables most related to a response variable, and incorporating unsupervised sparse PCA ensures that the final variable subset also captures the variance seen in the data beyond what is related to the response variable. The intersection of the variables selected using these methods can be used for powerful subsequent analysis, such as clustering and matching seen in this application.

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